

SOLVING OPTIMAL COMPONENTS ASSIGNMENT PROBLEM FOR A MULTISTATE NETWORK USING FUZZY OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Optimal components assignment problem subject to system reliability, total lead-time, and total cost constraints is studied in this paper. The problem is formulated as fuzzy linear problem using fuzzy membership functions. An approach based on genetic algorithm with fuzzy optimization to solve the presented problem. The optimal solution found by the proposed approach is characterized by maximum reliability, minimum total cost and minimum total lead-time. The proposed approach is tested on different examples taken from the literature to illustrate its efficiency in comparison with other previous methods.

KEYWORDS

Components Assignment Problem, Stochastic-Flow Networks, Network Reliability, Fuzzy Multi-Objective Linear Programming, Genetic Algorithms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Network reliability of stochastic-flow network (SFN) is defined as the probability that a specified amount of flow can be transmitted successfully from source to destination through SFN [1]. Components assignment problem (CAP) is one important problem in the field of system reliability analysis, finding an optimal component assignment is significant to maximize the system reliability and improve the system performance [2]. Many researchers studied CAP for a SFN to maximize the network reliability under different constraints, [3], proposed an algorithm to generate all minimal system states fulfilling the demand, time and budget constraints, then the system reliability is evaluated in terms of such system states. The authors in [4] focused on finding the optimal carrier selection based on network reliability criterion under a budget constraint, an optimization algorithm integrating a genetic algorithm, minimal paths and the recursive sum of disjoint products is proposed to solve such a problem. Multi-state CAP was discussed in [5] to maximize the network reliability under an assignment budget constraint, in which each component has an assignment cost, they suggested an optimization method based on genetic algorithm. In [6] they studied the optimal network line assignment with maximal network reliability and minimal total cost, they presented an approach based on Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) to solve multi-objective optimization for stochastic computer networks. In order to solve multi-objective CAP, [7], proposed two-stage approach to solving the multi-

objective CAP subject to reliability and assignment cost for SFN. In [8] he proposed an approach to get the exact optimal double-resource assignment for the robust design problem in multistate computer networks, a minimum capacity assignment for each link and node is searched to keep the network working even both links and nodes are subject to failures.

In the case of CAP for stochastic-flow network under lead-time constraint,[9], discussed this and he suggested Genetic Algorithm(GA) to search the optimal components for a minimum total lead-time that maximizes the system reliability, such that the total lead-time cannot exceed a specified amount. In addition, [10] studied multi-objective CAP subject to lead-time constraint they proposed GA based on the NSGA-II to search the optimal components that maximize the reliability. In the case of each component has both an assignment cost and lead-time constraints, [11], the CAP for SFN was studied and solved by a proposed approach based on a random weighted GA. The objective of proposed approach was to maximize the network reliability, minimize total lead-time and minimize cost.

The concept of decision making in the fuzzy environments is presented by [12]. In [13] illustrated that without increasing the computational effort, Fuzzy Linear Programming(FLP) problems can be solved. In addition, [14] presented general look at core ideas that make up the burgeoning body of fuzzy mathematical programming emphasizing the methodological view, and so [15] aggregated the concept of multi-objective programming application and using a membership function of the linear expression to represent and integrate each fuzzy objective, he let the solution is converted to another form of linear programming solution by using the way solve the application problem of fuzzy theory. Where in[16] they presented an inexact approach and recommended genetic algorithm to get a family of inexact solutions with acceptable membership degree to solve objective and resource type of FLP problems. A type of model of fuzzy quadratic programming problems is proposed in [17], according to different types of fuzzy resource constraints and fuzzy objective in actual production problems, they described the fuzzy objective and resource constraints with different type of membership functions. Furthermore, FLP problem formulations and membership functions were discussed by many researchers, [18 – 31] to apply FLP to various problems and improve the obtained solutions.

Recently, FLP is used to solve various problems [32-37]. By using a fuzzy multi-objective GA, [33] succeed in obtaining high quality solutions to solve the multi-objective decision problem. While in [34] they applied a fuzzy multi-objective linear programming model to combine the existed components with a new character by using an optimization method of the highest match. In [35] a new ranking methods of Subinterval average and subinterval addition is presented in order to solve FLP problem. A fuzzy linear programming model for a problem of food industry is presented and solved by [36] .The FLP is applied to the tri generation system (power generation, heat generation, and the generation of cooling effect), [37], to find the optimal design to the proposed system.

The aim of this paper is to solve the CAP for an SFN under system reliability, total lead time and total cost constraints. An approach based on fuzzy linear programming is presented to solve the CAP.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 illustrates needed notations. Section 3 presents the problem formulation. Next, section 4 illustrates the fuzzy linear formulation to the presented problem. Section 5 explains the proposed multi-objective GA based on fuzzy linear

programming. To demonstrate the usability of the proposed approach, several examples included in Section 6. Section 7 presents comparison and discussion, the last section shows conclusion.

2. NOTATIONS

N	No. of nodes.
$v \{a_e 1 \leq e \leq v\}$	No. of arcs.
MPs	Minimal paths.
np	Number of minimal paths.
mp_j	Minimal path no. j ; $j = 1, 2, \dots, np$.
vc	The number of available components.
vn_k	The components number k , $k = 1, 2, \dots, vc$.
$l(vn_k)$	Lead time of components vn_k .
$c(vn_k)$	Cost of components vn_k .
L_j	The lead time of mp_j .
$R_{d,T}$	The system reliability to the demand d under time limit T , for simplicity using R .
x	Capacity vector defined as $\mathcal{X} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_e)$.
P	$(p_1, p_2, \dots, p_v)$ The components assignment in which vn_k is assigned to the arc a_e if $p_e = k$.
$S_l(P)$	Total lead time.
$C(P)$	Total cost.
$\mathcal{S}$	Population size.
$\mathcal{G}$	Maximum number of generations.
gn	Generation number.
g_m	GA mutation rate.
g_c	GA crossover rate.
S_l^{obj}	Minimum acceptable feasible values of $S_l(P)$.
S_l^0	Maximum acceptable feasible values of $S_l(P)$.
R_{obj}	Maximum acceptable feasible values of R .
R_0	Minimum acceptable feasible values of R .
C_{obj}	Minimum acceptable feasible values of $C(P)$.
C_0	Maximum acceptable feasible values of $C(P)$.
$\mu(R)$	Fuzzy objective membership functions of R .
$\mu(S_l)$	Fuzzy objective membership functions of $S_l(P)$.
$\mu(C)$	Fuzzy objective membership functions of $C(P)$.
α	The acceptable membership degree level.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The mathematical programming formulation of the multi-objective optimization problem to maximize system reliability of a flow network, minimize the total lead-time and cost illustrating as follow:

$$\text{Maximize } R_{d,T}(P) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Minimize } S_l(P) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Minimize } C(P) \quad (3)$$

Subject to:

$$p_e = k, k \in \{1, 2, \dots, vc\} \text{ for } e = 1, 2, \dots, v. \quad (4)$$

$$p_e \neq p_h \text{ for } e \neq h \quad (5)$$

$$L_j \leq T, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, np \quad (6)$$

Where:

$$L_j = \sum_{e=1}^V l(p_e) \Big|_{p_e \in mp_j} \quad (7)$$

$$S_l(P) = \sum_{e=1}^V l(p_e) \quad (8)$$

$$C(P) = \sum_{e=1}^V C(p_e) \quad (9)$$

And, constraints (4) and (5) emphasize that each link should be given one component and that each component can be assigned to at most one link. All feasible component assignments are generated using constraints (4) and (5). Constraint (6) assures that the lead-time of the path MP_j (L_j) is less than the time limit (T), [9].

4. FUZZY LINEAR FORMULATION

To transform the mathematical formulation defined in section 3 into fuzzy linear formulation we will define that R_{obj} , S_l^{obj} and C_{obj} are the objective values with the consideration that

$$R \leq R_{obj}, S_l(P) \geq S_l^{obj}, C(P) \geq C_{obj}.$$

$$\mu(R) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } R > R_{obj} \\ 1 - \frac{R_{obj} - R}{\mathcal{P}_0} & \text{if } R_{obj} - \mathcal{P}_0 \leq R \leq R_{obj} \\ 0 & \text{if } R < R_0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\mu(S_l) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } S_l(P) < S_l^{obj} \\ 1 - \frac{S_l(P) - S_l^{obj}}{\mathcal{P}_1} & \text{if } S_l^{obj} \leq S_l(P) \leq S_l^{obj} + \mathcal{P}_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } S_l(P) > S_l^0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\mu(C) \begin{cases} 1 & \text{And, if } C(P) < C_{obj} \\ 1 - \frac{C(P) - C_{obj}}{\mathcal{P}_2} & \text{if } C_{obj} \leq C(P) \leq C_{obj} + \mathcal{P}_2 \\ 0 & \text{if } C(P) > C_0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where:

$\mathcal{P}_0$ Tolerance of $\mu(S_l)$, $\mathcal{P}_0 = R_{obj} - R_0$.

$\mathcal{P}_1$ Tolerance of $\mu(R)$, $\mathcal{P}_1 = S_l^0 - S_l^{obj}$.

$\mathcal{P}_2$ Tolerance of $\mu(C)$, $\mathcal{P}_2 = C_0 - C_{obj}$.

Hence, the membership function of the decision space $\bar{S}$ is $\mu_{\bar{S}}(P)$ is given by:

$$\text{Max } \mu_{\bar{S}}(P) = \text{Max}\{0, \min\{\mu(R), \mu(S_l), \mu(C)\}\} \quad (13)$$

5. THE GENETIC ALGORITHM

5.1. Chromosome Representation

The chromosome P contains v fields, where v is the number of arcs (components) for the network. Each field in ch represents the components number assigned to an arc.

$$P = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_v)$$

Where p_1, p_2 and p_v are random component numbers between 1 and vc , this means that the component p_1 is assigned to arc a_1 , the component p_2 is assigned to arc $a_2, \dots$ and the component p_v is assigned to arc a_v .

5.2. Initial Population

The initial population is generated according to the following steps:

Step 1: randomly generate chromosome P in the initial population in the form:

$$P = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_v).$$

Step 2: calculate $R, C(P)$ and $S_l(P)$.

Step 3: calculate the membership function of the decision space $\mu_{\bar{S}}(P)$ using equation 13.

Step 4: if $\mu_{\bar{S}}(P)$ of the generated chromosome in step 1 is less than α discard it and go to step 1.

Step 5: repeat step 1 to 3 to generate $\mathcal{S}$ chromosomes.

5.3. The Fitness Function

We take the membership function of the fuzzy optimal solution, $\mu_{\bar{S}}(P)$ as the fitness function F of the genetic algorithm.

5.4. Genetic Selection

We will use the roulette wheel selection method to select the parent population to the next generation from the current population as follows:

Step 1: calculate a cumulative probability for each chromosome $pr(gn)$, $gn = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{S}$ by:

$$pr(gn) = \frac{\mu_{\bar{S}}(P)}{\sum_{gn=1}^{\mathcal{S}} \mu_{\bar{S}}(P) + \varepsilon} \quad (14)$$

Where ε is a small positive integer, it is used to guarantee a nonzero denominator.

Step 2: generate random real number r in $[0, 1]$.

Step 3: if $r \leq pr(1)$, select the first chromosome, otherwise select the gn_{th} chromosome

($2 \leq gn \leq \mathcal{S}$) if $pr(gn - 1) < r \leq pr(gn)$.

Step 4: Repeat steps 2 and 3, $\mathcal{S}$ times and obtain $\mathcal{S}$ chromosomes.

5.5. Genetic Crossover Operation

In the proposed GA, uniform crossover is used to breed a child from two parents by randomly taking a component from the corresponding component of the child as shown in fig.1. The crossover operation is performed as follows:

- Step 1: select two chromosome according to the selection strategy, section 5.4.
- Step 2: randomly take a component from one of the two chromosomes to form a corresponding components of the child.
- Step3: repeat step 2 until the components of the child fill up perfectly.

Figure 1. Uniform crossover operator

5.6. Genetic Mutation Operation

A child undergoes mutation according to the mutation probability g_m and the mutation probability for each component g_m .

- Step 1: generate a random number $r_1 \in [0,1]$.
- Step 2: if $r_1 < g_m$, the chromosome is chosen to mutate and go to step 3, otherwise skip this chromosome.
- Step 3: for each component of the child do:
 - Step 3.1: Generate a random number $r_2 \in [0,1]$.
 - Step 3.2: if $r_2 < g_m$ then mutate this component as follows:
 - Step 3.2.1: if $p_j = vn_k$, then randomly choose one in $\{1,2, \dots, vc\} - \{vn_k\}$.
 - Step 3.2.2: if previous step does not achieve skip this component.

Figure 2 shows an example of performing the mutation operation on a given chromosome.

Figure 2. Mutation operation

5.7. The Proposed Algorithm

This section presents the proposed GA for solving the multi-objective optimization problem to maximize system reliability of a flow network, minimize the total lead-time and cost which described in section 3, with its fuzzy linear optimization presented in section 4. the steps of this algorithm are as follow:

- Step 1: Set the parameters: $S, \phi, g_m, g_c, S_l^{obj}, S_l^0, R_{obj}, R_0, C_{obj}, C_0$ and α .
- Step 2: Generate the initial population and calculate the membership function for each chromosome in it according to equations 10, 11, 12 and 13.
- Step 3: Calculate the fitness function $\mu_{\bar{s}}(P)$ and cumulative probability $pr(gn)$ for each chromosome P in the current population using equation 13,14.

- Step 4: In the new generation set $k = 0$.
- Step 5: To obtain one child select two chromosomes from the current population according to g_c , apply crossover then mutate the new child according to g_m parameter.
- Step 6: Evaluate the current child (P) by calculating $\mu_{\bar{s}}(P)$.
- Step 7: If $\mu_{\bar{s}}(P) \geq \alpha$ then increment k . Otherwise go to step 5.
- Step 8: If $gn < S$ then goto step 9.
- Step 9: Save best solution with high $\mu_{\bar{s}}(P)$.
- Step 10: Set $gn = gn + 1$.
- Step 11: If $gn = g_{exit}$, otherwise go to step 4.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section we illustrated the results of applying the proposed approach on three networks, four nodes, six nodes and TANET (Taiwan Academic Network). The genetic parameters used in the proposed GA are: $S = 10, g = 100, g_c = 0.95, g_m = 0.05, 0.3 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$.

6.1. Four Node Network Example

The network shown in Figure3 has four nodes and six arcs. The capacity, probability, lead-time and cost of each component (vn) is shown in Table1. There are six minimal paths: $mp_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}, mp_2 = \{a_1, a_5, a_8\}, mp_3 = \{a_1, a_2, a_6\}, mp_4 = \{a_1, a_2, a_7, a_8\}, mp_5 = \{a_3, a_6\}$ and $mp_6 = \{a_3, a_7, a_8\}$. We studied different values for T under different values of α when $d=4$ as illustrated in table 2, 3, 4, 5. where $c_{obj} = 200, c_0 = 250, R_{obj} = 0.99, R = 0.9, S_{obj} = 9, S_0 = 12$.

Figure3. Computer network with 4 nodes and 6 arcs

Table 1. Components capacities, probabilities, lead-time and cost.

vn_k	Capacity							$l(vn_k)$	$c(vn_k)$
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6		
1	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.97	2	10
2	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.15	0.20	0.50	0	3	60
3	0.07	0.08	0.00	0.85	0	0	0	2	10
4	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0	2	20
5	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.94	1	50

6	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.98	3	60
7	0.50	0.50	0	0	0	0	0	3	20
8	0.25	0.25	0.50	0	0	0	0	1	50
9	0.15	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	2	80
10	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.90	0	0	0	2	100

Table 2. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.3, when T=6.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
4,6	0.3	0.6	0.991259	10	220	5 9 4 8 1 3
	0.4	0.6	0.988174	10	220	8 5 4 3 9 1
	0.5	0.6	0.959904	10	220	8 5 4 3 1 9
	0.6	0.6	0.988120	10	220	4 5 8 9 3 1

Table 3. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.3, when T=7.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
4,7	0.3	0.4	0.975702	10	230	3 9 4 8 1 5
	0.4	0.6	0.969527	10	220	9 3 8 1 5 4
	0.5	0.6	0.980725	10	220	8 3 4 9 1 5
	0.6	0.6	0.987968	10	220	8 5 3 9 4 1

Table 4. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.3, when T=8.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
4,8	0.3	0.6	0.996651	10	220	9 1 8 4 3 5
	0.4	0.6	0.996418	10	220	5 9 4 8 1 3
	0.5	0.6	0.972226	10	220	3 9 1 8 5 4
	0.6	0.6	0.987288	10	220	4 1 3 9 8 5

Table 5. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.3, when T=9.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
4,9	0.3	0.6	0.990578	10	220	5 9 4 8 3 1
	0.4	0.6	0.986147	10	220	8 5 4 1 9 3
	0.5	0.6	0.962853	10	220	3 9 4 1 8 5
	0.6	0.6	0.995077	10	220	9 1 3 4 8 5

6.2. Six-Node Network Example

The network has six nodes and 9 links (Fig. 4), [9].The *MPs* are as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}
 mp_1 &= \{a_1, a_4, a_9\}, mp_2 = \{a_1, a_4, a_7, a_8\}, mp_3 = \{a_1, a_5, a_8\}, mp_4 = \{a_1, a_5, a_7, a_9\}, \\
 mp_5 &= \{a_1, a_3, a_6, a_8\}, mp_6 = \{a_1, a_3, a_6, a_7, a_9\}, mp_7 = \{a_2, a_6, a_8\}, mp_8 = \{a_2, a_6, a_7, a_9\}, \\
 mp_9 &= \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_9\}, mp_{10} = \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_7, a_8\}, mp_{11} = \{a_2, a_3, a_5, a_8\}, mp_{12} = \{a_2, a_3, a_5, a_7, a_9\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We studied different values for d, T under different values for α as illustrated in table 7, 8,9,10 .where

$$c_{obj} = 450, c_0 = 550, R_{obj} = 0.99, R_0 = 0.9, S_{obj} = 14, S_0 = 19.$$

Figure 4. The six-nodes network example

Table 6. Arc capacity, probability, lead-time, and cost for the 20 available components

vn_k	Capacity							$l(vn_k)$	$c(vn_k)$
	0	1		3	4	5	6		
1	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.97	2	10
2	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.15	0.20	0.50	0	3	60
3	0.07	0.08	0.00	0.85	0	0	0	2	10
4	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0	2	20
5	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.94	1	50
6	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.98	3	60
7	0.50	0.50	0	0	0	0	0	3	20
8	0.25	0.25	0.50	0	0	0	0	1	50
9	0.15	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	2	80
10	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.90	0	0	0	2	100
11	0.01	0.99	0	0	0	0	0	1	70
12	0.02	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.88	1	60
13	0.07	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.65	0	3	10
14	0.05	0.05	0.90	0	0	0	0	2	20
15	0.60	0.40	0	0	0	0	0	2	50
16	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.85	0	0	1	60
17	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.70	0	0	0	1	20
18	0.70	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.30	0	3	50
19	0.07	0.18	0.75	0	0	0	0	2	80
20	0.40	0.40	0.20	0	0	0	0	3	100

Table 7. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.4, when $d=6, T=7$.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
6,7	0.3	0.915	0.982329	12	500	17 12 8 14 1 10 11 5 16
	0.4	0.845	0.976077	12	430	12 11 8 14 1 15 17 5 16
	0.5	0.940	0.984567	12	420	17 12 8 1 3 10 16 5 11
	0.6	0.773	0.969599	12	410	8 5 11 3 9 10 17 12 16
	0.7	0.987	0.988833	12	440	5 16 11 1 19 14 8 17 12
	0.8	0.948	0.985344	12	450	12 17 11 3 1 19 16 5 8

Table 8. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.4, when d=6, T=8.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
6,8	0.3	0.991	0.989161	14	500	12 17 16 15 10 3 5 14 1
	0.4	0.999	0.989945	12	460	5 17 11 10 12 16 8 1 9
	0.5	0.972	0.987453	12	510	5 16 11 12 10 8 17 1 9
	0.6	0.981	0.988298	12	430	10 8 17 1 16 11 15 5 12
	0.7	0.972	0.987471	13	330	5 10 17 1 14 3 16 8 12
	0.8	0.990	0.989110	12	460	12 17 8 5 19 15 11 4 1

Table 9. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.4, when d=6, T=9.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
6,9	0.3	0.992	0.989316	14	440	3 11 14 9 19 12 16 5 4
	0.4	0.978	0.987985	14	390	14 17 11 9 10 12 3 5 4
	0.5	0.997	0.989773	14	420	3 11 8 9 14 12 15 5 1
	0.6	0.997	0.989724	14	440	12 16 17 1 19 10 4 5 9
	0.7	0.981	0.988318	13	380	1 17 14 5 3 11 10 12 8
	0.8	0.926	0.983324	14	510	5 10 11 17 16 14 4 1 15

Table 10. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.4, when d=8, T=9.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
8,9	0.3	0.999	0.989896	14	420	5 9 4 1 10 19 17 16 12
	0.4	0.999	0.989895	14	350	12 17 16 1 9 10 4 19 5
	0.5	0.994	0.989474	14	400	12 3 19 5 9 10 16 1 17
	0.6	0.992	0.989280	13	510	5 1 17 16 12 3 8 10 14
	0.7	0.984	0.988565	14	410	12 1 17 9 19 10 8 5 3
	0.8	0.986	0.988716	14	500	1 19 11 3 12 9 14 5 16

6.3. THE TANET EXAMPLE

In this section, we study the Taiwan Academic Network (TANET) with 30 and 33 links. The available 80 components are shown in Table 11, [7], in addition, we study TANET with 33 links using different components information shown in table 20, [38].

6.3.1. The TANET with 30 Links

TANET with one source and one sink as shown in figure 5 has 6 MPs found by [7]. The 6 paths are as follows: $mp_1 = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9, a_{10}, a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{13}\}$, $mp_2 = \{a_1, a_2, a_{21}, a_{15}, a_{16}, a_{17}, a_{19}, a_{20}\}$, $mp_3 = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, a_8, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{20}\}$, $mp_4 = \{a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}, a_{17}, a_{19}, a_{20}\}$, $mp_5 = \{a_{22}, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{28}\}$, $mp_6 = \{a_{22}, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{29}, a_{30}\}$.

The corresponding lead-time for each component is randomly assigned in this article. We studied different values for d, T under different values for α as illustrated in table 14, 15, 16, 17. Where $c_{obj} = 1700, c_0 = 2000, R_{obj} = 0.999, R_0 = 0.9, S_{obj} = 66, S_0 = 80$.

Table 11. Component information.

vn_k	Capacity					$l(vn_k)$	$c(vn_k)$
	0	1	2	3	4		
1	0.0004	0.0392	0.9604	0	0	1	10
2	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	1	60
3	0.000343	0.013671	0.181629	0.804357	0	1	10
4	0.015	0.985	0	0	0	2	20
5	0.0016	0.0768	0.9216	0	0	2	50
6	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	60
7	0.003	0	0.997	0	0	2	20
8	0.007225	0	0.15555	0	0.837225	1	50
9	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	80
10	0.003	0.997	0	0	0	2	100
11	0.034	0.966	0	0	0	2	70
12	0.0036	0.1128	0.8836	0	0	3	75
13	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	2	85
14	0.000784	0.054432	0.944784	0	0	1	35
15	0.000225	0.02955	0.970225	0	0	1	45
16	0.095	0.905	0	0	0	3	20
17	0.005776	0.140448	0.853776	0	0	3	30
18	0.000625	0.04875	0.950625	0	0	2	30
19	0.000729	0.022113	0.223587	0.753571	0	1	40
20	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	2	30
21	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	1	30
22	0.004225	0.12155	0.874225	0	0	3	60
23	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	80
24	0.003	0	0.997	0	0	2	90
25	0.000216	0.010152	0.159048	0.830584	0	3	100
26	0.034	0.966	0	0	0	2	65
27	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	2	75
28	0.000343	0.013671	0.181629	0.80435	0	1	85
29	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	3	40
30	0.0009	0.0582	0.9409	0	0	2	40
31	0.002809	0.100382	0.896809	0	0	1	50
32	0.000166375	0.008575875	0.147349125	0.843908625	0	2	50
33	0.000125	0.007125	0.135375	0.857375	0	2	50
34	0.0001	0.0198	0.9801	0	0	1	60
35	0.025	0.975	0	0	0	3	60
36	0.024	0.976	0	0	0	3	30
37	0.000125	0.007125	0.135375	0.857375	0	2	30
38	0.000110592	0.006580224	0.130507776	0.862801408	0	1	30
39	0.0001	0	0.0198	0	0.9801	1	30
40	0.001849	0	0.082302	0	0.915849	3	40
41	0.001024	0.061952	0.937024	0	0	2	70
42	0.000676	0.050648	0.948676	0	0	2	70

43	0.007921	0.162158	0.829921	0	0	4	80
44	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	2	80
45	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	5	90
46	0.097	0	0.903	0	0	4	95
47	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	3	20
48	0.022	0.978		0	0	2	20
49	0.000256	0	0.031488	0	0.968256	1	20
50	0.001225	0	0.06755	0	0.931225	1	20
51	0.025	0.975	0	0	0	3	25
52	0.000274625	0.011851125	0.170473875	0.817400375	0.000274625	2	25
53	0.000529	0	0.044942	0	0.954529	3	30
54	0.000144	0	0.023712	0	0.976144	1	60
55	0.000216	0.010152	0.159048	0.830584	0	2	70
56	0.000117649	0.006850053	0.132946947	0.860085351	0	1	70
57	0.046	0	0.954	0	0	2	80
58	0.083	0	0.917	0	0	3	60
59	0.000015625	0.001828125	0.071296875	0.926859375	0	3	60
60	0.000274625	0.011851125	0.170473875	0.817400375	0	2	10
61	0.001369	0.071262	0.927369	0	0	2	10
62	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	2	15
63	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	3	15
64	0.006084	0.143832	0.850084	0	0	2	25
65	0.004096	0.119808	0.876096	0	0	5	25
66	0.003481	0.111038	0.885481	0	0	4	55
67	0.035	0.965	0	0	0	2	55
68	0.022	0	0.978	0	0	3	70
69	0.000166375	0.008575875	0.147349125	0.843908625	0	3	70
70	0.000042875	0.003546375	0.097778625	0.898632125	0	3	70
71	0.000024389	0.002449833	0.082027167	0.915498611	0	2	60
72	0.000324	0	0.035352	0	0.964324	1	50
73	0.000000343	0.000145971	0.020707029	0.979146657	0	2	40
74	0.004356	0.123288	0.872356	0	0	3	40
75	0.055	0.945	0	0	0	2	40
76	0.001936	0.084128	0.913936	0	0	5	80
77	0.000035937	0.003159189	0.092573811	0.904231063	0	4	100
78	0.000484	0	0.043032	0	0.956484	2	100
79	0.000121	0	0.021758	0	0.978121	1	40
80	0.001	0.999	0	0	0	2	60

Figure 5. TANET with 30links

Figure 6. TANET with 33 links

Table 12. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.5, when d=4, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
4,16	0.3	0.565	0.999614	42	1485	8 79 54 28 49 34 37 42 2 1 14 9 39 13 61 64 72 23 56 55 41 52 31 78 5 4 19 32 48 73
	0.4	0.991	0.998111	43	1485	28 8 10 1 14 79 64 50 3 21 56 54 19 6 11 48 57 60 23 15 44 30 26 4 78 2 73 72 39 71
	0.5	0.937	0.992714	44	1440	8 79 54 28 49 34 37 42 2 1 14 9 39 13 31 64 72 23 56 55 41 52 61 78 5 4 19 32 48 73
	0.6	0.993	0.998347	43	1460	34 6 50 27 54 49 31 39 2 21 75 79 1 24 20 73 44 30 64 56 71 19 9 67 52 28 14 37 57 8
	0.7	0.989	0.997924	46	1340	14 3 21 50 8 23 5 28 79 1 56 39 10 80 37 4 61 33 71 49 78 55 27 19 52 20 54 44 7 41
	0.8	0.992	0.998211	45	1340	9 38 34 19 8 28 14 56 78 79 31 6 60 49 15 75 44 21 71 1 13 30 27 10 37 61 26 42 7 80

Table 13. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.5, when d=6, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
6,16	0.3	0.998	0.998768	40	1475	9 4 1 39 54 56 31 38 80 6 72 28 19 23 34 57 21 44 49 27 18 30 61 73 24 79 32 71 50 14
	0.4	0.998	0.998782	42	1615	72 21 34 56 3 28 8 50 6 71 67 1 19 73 23 15 13 38 78 39 49 37 61 31 26 18 48 79 41 4

	0.5	0.996	0.998603	44	1615	50 28 1 32 15 54 39 2 34 72 37 14 49 57 5 60 67 61 23 79 33 19 30 55 27 7 3 78 38 18
	0.6	0.987	0.997724	41	1480	79 19 1 6 42 33 38 2 72 39 54 8 49 21 10 31 14 80 75 3 4 56 23 60 13 55 44 15 73 34
	0.7	0.999	0.998926	41	1345	2 28 49 31 8 54 79 39 52 18 6 50 72 33 14 73 38 27 61 71 3 1 44 23 13 60 15 20 19 21
	0.8	0.999	0.998934	42	1485	9 4 1 39 54 56 31 38 80 6 72 28 19 23 34 57 21 44 49 27 18 30 61 73 24 79 32 71 50 14

Table 14. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.5, when d=8, T=18.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
8,18	0.3	0.960	0.995038	44	1345	14 6 72 64 49 56 55 54 80 31 60 9 39 75 34 38 15 73 4 67 1 62 3 18 2 23 79 57 20 24
	0.4	0.998	0.998810	43	1425	31 28 72 2 49 39 6 3 80 1 60 56 14 18 34 19 15 50 4 10 26 7 9 79 55 44 64 30 20 5
	0.5	0.996	0.998596	44	1425	72 44 3 2 20 15 28 27 78 21 19 8 14 32 73 61 23 38 1 9 26 54 71 31 5 33 49 42 52 62
	0.6	0.990	0.998026	46	1390	14 6 72 64 49 56 55 54 80 31 60 9 39 75 34 38 15 73 4 67 1 62 3 18 2 23 79 57 20 24
	0.7	0.981	0.997163	46	1390	32 56 6 49 48 42 54 9 2 23 18 3 79 44 11 34 20 61 21 67 26 14 7 8 39 1 71 57 55 15
	0.8	0.969	0.995945	44	1580	21 6 49 8 27 72 2 44 24 28 52 9 54 32 57 67 13 75 50 4 79 33 31 73 39 62 23 56 38 41

Table 15. Optimal solutions founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.5, when d=9, T=18.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
9,18	0.3	0.972	0.996221	45	1580	23 71 38 1 21 26 78 5 2 34 54 15 50 62 33 42 60 61 3 49 48 56 32 13 6 7 14 27 73 8
	0.4	0.980	0.997066	43	1320	23 71 19 1 39 26 28 5 38 34 21 15 79 62 27 42 9 61 3 49 60 56 32 13 54 7 50 33 78 8
	0.5	0.975	0.996522	46	1320	32 30 54 2 48 19 23 1 38 3 18 49 79 57 11 8 20 37 21 27 26 78 7 60 39 52 71 6 55 34
	0.6	0.988	0.997803	46	1430	79 3 21 61 78 62 15 49 28 31 64 6 39 32 7 80 67 48 4 75 60 55 38 56 34 50 13 23 24 20
	0.7	0.990	0.997983	44	1515	60 72 28 9 54 23 56 67 55 34 30 38 3 62 78 64 37 52 32 50 42 14 13 1 31 39 48 71 15 8
	0.8	0.915	0.990616	45	1450	19 21 3 61 39 49 72 73 38 79 52 37 2 13 57 33 24 6 27 20 60 56 34 55 54 30 50 7 78 14

6.3.2. The TANET with 33 Links

TANET with two sources and two sinks shown in Figure 6, it has 14 MPs found by [38]. The 14 paths are as follows:

$$mp_1 = \{a_4, a_{32}, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{12}, a_{13}, a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}\}, mp_2 = \{a_4, a_{32}, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{20}, a_{21}, a_{22}\},$$

$$mp_3 = \{a_5, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{12}, a_{13}, a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}\}, mp_4 = \{a_5, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{20}, a_{21}, a_{22}\},$$

$mp_5 = \{a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9, a_{10}, a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{13}, a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}\}, mp_6 = \{a_6, a_7, a_8, a_9, a_{10}, a_{11}, a_{20}, a_{21}, a_{22}\},$
 $mp_7 = \{a_1, a_{32}, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{12}, a_{13}, a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}\}, mp_8 = \{a_1, a_{32}, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{20}, a_{21}, a_{22}\},$
 $mp_9 = \{a_5, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{12}, a_{13}, a_{14}, a_{15}, a_{16}\}, mp_{10} = \{a_2, a_{17}, a_{18}, a_{19}, a_{20}, a_{21}, a_{22}\},$
 $mp_{11} = \{a_3, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{28}\}, mp_{12} = \{a_3, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{29}\},$
 $mp_{13} = \{a_3, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{33}, a_{30}\}, mp_{14} = \{a_3, a_{23}, a_{24}, a_{25}, a_{26}, a_{27}, a_{33}, a_{31}\}.$
 We studied different values for d, T under different values for α as illustrated in table 19, 20, 21, 22. Where $C_{obj} = 1700, c_0 = 2000, R_{obj} = 0.999, R_0 = 0.9, S_{obj} = 66, S_0 = 80.$

Table 16. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=4, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_I(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
4,16	0.3	0.989	0.999782	60	1725	69 75 11 36 45 71 67 56 27 15 1 50 72 23 3 21 34 14 12 2 5 41 39 60 33 20 38 37 22 64 43 42 19
	0.4	0.989	0.999916	56	1665	57 18 72 40 17 8 31 21 15 43 30 54 56 14 6 3 2 49 62 73 38 24 35 16 1 50 79 58 71 10 67 11 7
	0.5	0.999	0.998866	60	1653	27 2 14 67 5 75 54 38 52 78 3 28 7 50 8 19 23 62 20 71 58 9 15 68 31 13 69 11 79 60 32 80 44
	0.6	0.986	0.997640	60	1585	29 4 56 69 68 32 52 50 6 21 9 28 75 38 15 71 10 31 3 79 41 33 48 8 19 44 72 78 42 76 30 34 11
	0.7	0.986	0.997638	53	1675	24 1 8 12 58 32 11 4 28 15 72 21 67 6 2 3 5 79 44 71 49 31 16 60 26 19 57 78 30 9 38 39 42
	0.8	0.997	0.998729	56	1480	4 78 31 33 74 71 38 3 1 72 63 50 56 8 64 79 80 5 9 2 14 53 77 15 30 55 7 61 23 37 13 52 49

Table 17. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=6, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_I(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
6,16	0.3	0.991	0.998143	58	1495	17 23 39 16 67 1 5 22 79 72 15 10 8 3 49 54 52 28 60 24 32 6 9 64 44 37 31 18 73 58 51 56 80
	0.4	0.742	0.973425	57	1520	57 18 71 40 17 8 31 21 15 43 30 54 56 14 6 3 2 49 62 73 38 24 35 16 1 50 79 58 72 10 67 11 7
	0.5	0.999	0.998894	58	1580	18 56 23 48 65 11 26 8 9 28 44 19 61 31 49 6 21 79 34 64 39 51 42 1 4 3 33 25 29 24 12 50 59
	0.6	0.941	0.993122	55	1695	73 31 11 61 53 2 13 21 78 32 57 39 54 38 19 49 6 27 28 8 37 14 17 15 1 23 50 76 24 4 56 41 69
	0.7	0.988	0.997793	61	1615	1 67 13 32 45 37 2 15 57 75 34 38 78 50 39 3 19 24 9 61 8 71 23 40 14 55 21 41 22 51 17 73 7
	0.8	0.956	0.994633	53	1675	24 1 8 12 58 32 11 4 28 15 72 21 67 6 2 3 5 39 44 71 49 31 16 60 26 19 57 78 30 9 38 79 42

Table 18. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in in fig.6, when d=8, T=18.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
8,18	0.3	0.705	0.969841	58	1745	44 46 21 80 1 6 26 33 23 39 40 34 14 28 12 79 15 4 55 20 70 18 50 37 71 49 7 24 30 65 56 42 75
	0.4	0.848	0.983954	60	1715	13 68 24 31 76 72 39 56 38 50 25 6 48 9 11 10 79 14 34 47 8 30 18 59 37 21 15 16 17 26 12 3 23
	0.5	0.586	0.957987	60	1615	55 40 5 17 20 73 49 30 6 4 32 10 71 21 1 2 67 56 9 34 14 3 24 75 28 19 53 54 65 42 23 22 51
	0.6	0.939	0.992971	64	1695	17 35 1 70 68 38 14 11 56 52 53 54 20 79 26 3 33 32 4 27 61 19 15 64 34 60 49 72 66 41 5 28 40
	0.7	0.984	0.997378	59	1745	18 20 14 5 17 71 4 31 47 9 8 19 15 60 27 3 44 80 21 74 75 42 6 23 2 10 28 51 54 39 69 59 56
	0.8	0.998	0.998795	62	1635	12 49 34 66 58 6 73 28 5 52 19 54 56 33 39 8 44 69 3 62 30 42 50 29 23 71 63 68 61 25 53 15 31

Table 19: optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=9, T=18.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	$C(p)$	Assigned components
9,18	0.3	0.807	0.979884	64	1770	44 46 21 80 1 6 26 33 23 39 40 34 14 28 12 79 15 4 55 20 70 18 50 37 71 49 7 24 30 65 56 42 75
	0.4	0.878	0.986876	60	1770	67 24 10 51 28 52 34 19 33 48 21 79 1 64 13 42 23 54 9 65 49 8 22 57 41 62 27 12 43 36 7 26 6
	0.5	0.844	0.983599	57	1645	18 20 14 5 17 71 4 31 47 9 8 19 15 60 27 3 44 80 21 74 75 42 6 23 2 10 28 51 54 39 69 59 56
	0.6	0.985	0.997503	57	1630	12 57 66 8 58 34 73 21 54 28 19 71 72 6 44 14 52 5 78 70 30 3 50 56 23 59 63 39 61 49 53 79 31
	0.7	0.888	0.987891	58	1600	3 34 80 71 42 47 18 56 8 30 26 15 21 28 49 20 59 37 54 57 7 50 79 69 78 12 36 40 9 39 64 52 23
	0.8	0.968	0.995783	66	1545	52 53 7 17 15 56 55 11 28 79 67 5 60 71 49 23 72 10 21 32 6 38 76 26 4 39 24 73 40 9 50 30 80

6.3.3. The TANET with 33 links and different components information

As shown in section 6.3.2.TANET has 33 links and 14 MPs. We studied different values for d, T under different values for α ,when $\alpha = 0.5,0.6,0.7$ and 0.8 no solutions found as illustrated in table 21,when

$\alpha = 0.6,0.7$ and 0.8 no solutions found as illustrated in table 22, 23, 24.Where $C_{obj} = 1700, c_0 = 3000, R_{obj} = 0.999, R_0 = 0.9, S_{obj} = 66, S_0 = 80$.

Table 20. Component information.

vn_k	Capacity					$l(vn_k)$	$c(vn_k)$
	0	1	2	3	4		
1	0.0004	0.0392	0.9604	0	0	1	100
2	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	1	50
3	0.000343	0.013671	0.181629	0.804357	0	1	65
4	0.015	0.985	0	0	0	2	80
5	0.0016	0.0768	0.9216	0	0	2	70
6	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	135
7	0.003	0	0.997	0	0	2	60
8	0.007225	0	0.15555	0	0.837225	1	35
9	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	35
10	0.003	0.997	0	0	0	2	80
11	0.034	0.966	0	0	0	2	55
12	0.0036	0.1128	0.8836	0	0	3	40
13	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	2	110
14	0.000784	0.054432	0.944784	0	0	1	65
15	0.000225	0.02955	0.970225	0	0	1	70
16	0.095	0.905	0	0	0	3	15
17	0.005776	0.140448	0.853776	0	0	3	35
18	0.000625	0.04875	0.950625	0	0	2	75
19	0.000729	0.022113	0.223587	0.753571	0	1	40
20	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	2	35
21	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	1	45
22	0.004225	0.12155	0.874225	0	0	3	30
23	0.005929	0	0.142142	0	0.851929	1	85
24	0.003	0	0.997	0	0	2	70
25	0.000216	0.010152	0.159048	0.830584	0	3	55
26	0.034	0.966	0	0	0	2	30
27	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	2	55
28	0.000343	0.013671	0.181629	0.804357	0	1	60
29	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	3	35
30	0.0009	0.0582	0.9409	0	0	2	85
31	0.002809	0.100382	0.896809	0	0	1	60
32	0.000166375	0.008575875	0.147349125	0.843908625	0	2	70
33	0.000125	0.007125	0.135375	0.857375	0	2	80
34	0.0001	0.0198	0.9801	0	0	1	140
35	0.025	0.975	0	0	0	3	10
36	0.024	0.976	0	0	0	3	60
37	0.000125	0.007125	0.135375	0.857375	0	2	75
38	0.000110592	0.006580224	0.130507776	0.862801408	0	1	85
39	0.0001	0	0.0198	0	0.9801	1	100
40	0.001849	0	0.082302	0	0.915849	3	60
41	0.001024	0.061952	0.937024	0	0	2	60
42	0.000676	0.050648	0.948676	0	0	2	65
43	0.007921	0.162158	0.829921	0	0	4	35
44	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	2	25
45	0.001	0.027	0.243	0.729	0	5	20
46	0.097	0	0.903	0	0	4	40
47	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	3	135
48	0.022	0.978	0	0	0	2	70
49	0.000256	0	0.031488	0	0.968256	1	145
50	0.001225	0	0.06755	0	0.931225	1	70
51	0.025	0.975	0	0	0	3	70
52	0.000274625	0.011851125	0.170473875	0.817400375	0	2	65

53	0.000529	0	0.044942	0	0.954529	3	120
54	0.000144	0	0.023712	0	0.976144	1	110
55	0.000216	0.010152	0.159048	0.830584	0	2	70
56	0.000117649	0.006850053	0.132946947	0.860085351	0	1	60
57	0.046	0	0.954	0	0	2	50
58	0.083	0	0.917	0	0	3	40
59	0.000015625	0.001828125	0.071296875	0.926859375	0	3	105
60	0.000274625	0.011851125	0.170473875	0.817400375	0	2	60
61	0.001369	0.071262	0.927369	0	0	2	85
62	0.000001	0.000297	0.029403	0.970299	0	2	125
63	0.000512	0.017664	0.203136	0.778688	0	3	50
64	0.006084	0.143832	0.850084	0	0	2	40
65	0.004096	0.119808	0.876096	0	0	5	45
66	0.003481	0.111038	0.885481	0	0	4	50
67	0.035	0.965	0	0	0	2	60
68	0.022	0	0.978	0	0	3	70
69	0.000166375	0.008575875	0.147349125	0.843908625	0	3	85
70	0.000042875	0.003546375	0.097778625	0.898632125	0	3	95
71	0.000024389	0.002449833	0.082027167	0.915498611	0	2	100
72	0.000324	0	0.035352	0	0.964324	1	95
73	0.000000343	0.000145971	0.020707029	0.979146657	0	2	145
74	0.004356	0.123288	0.872356	0	0	3	30
75	0.055	0.945	0	0	0	2	15
76	0.001936	0.084128	0.913936	0	0	5	55
77	0.000035937	0.003159189	0.092573811	0.904231063	0	4	85
78	0.000484	0	0.043032	0	0.956484	2	115
79	0.000121	0	0.021758	0	0.978121	1	100
80	0.001	0.999	0	0	0	2	100

Table 21. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=4, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
4,16	0.3	0.535	0.998911	56	2335	57 18 72 40 17 8 31 21 15 43 30 54 56 14 6 3 2 49 62 73 38 24 35 16 1 50 79 58 71 10 67 11 7
	0.4	0.577	0.996485	60	2250	47 63 1 8 77 19 9 64 54 11 68 72 6 14 31 15 41 55 39 24 23 34 20 36 37 67 2 25 46 32 26 44 21

Table 22. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=6, T=16.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
6,16	0.3	0.419	0.989936	58	2285	17 23 39 16 67 1 5 22 79 72 15 10 8 3 49 54 52 28 60 24 32 6 9 64 44 37 31 18 73 58 51 56 80
	0.4	0.469	0.980578	61	2160	29 4 56 69 68 32 52 50 6 21 9 28 75 38 15 71 10 31 3 79 41 33 48 8 19 44 72 78 42 76 30 34 11
	0.5	0.515	0.992262	60	2225	1 67 13 32 45 37 2 15 57 75 34 38 78 50 39 3 19 24 9 61 8 71 23 40 14 55 21 41 22 51 17 73 7

Table 23. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in in fig.6, when d=8, T=18.

d,t	α	best μ_s	$R_{d,t}$	$S_1(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
8,18	0.3	0.350	0.940637	62	2335	61 59 1 31 68 38 4 79 48 23 73 34 9 3 72 50 54 46 78 16 42 10 19 56 55 5 17 35 76

						69 8 21 33
	0.4	0.438	0.991574	61	2305	71 59 39 53 5 11 60 78 72 8 64 44 28 14 30 9 26 54 31 52 56 37 20 23 2 79 1 43 74 10 33 38 13
	0.5	0.538	0.997141	59	2465	24 12 61 53 77 40 6 21 7 52 60 48 1 3 72 34 8 9 38 15 23 62 59 42 54 50 29 41 32 75 55 79 20

Table 24. Optimal results founded by proposed approach to the network in fig.6, when d=9, T=18.

d,t	α	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	Assigned components
9,18	0.3	0.496	0.989470	57	2080	44 46 21 80 1 6 26 33 23 39 40 34 14 28 12 79 15 4 55 20 70 18 50 37 71 49 7 24 30 65 56 42 75
	0.4	0.512	0.999175	63	2430	18 68 15 25 27 72 31 56 53 50 61 6 2 9 19 10 67 14 75 12 48 30 38 59 13 47 34 16 39 26 24 3 51
	0.5	0.627	0.966636	61	2295	46 67 73 26 13 18 42 44 21 59 61 79 56 19 1 23 9 38 52 5 15 27 55 3 8 39 4 65 74 63 30 28 62

7. DISCUSSION AND COMPARISON

This section presents a comparison between the proposed algorithm and that one proposed by Aissou et al.,[11] based on RWGA. Table 25 and 26 show the comparison results for two studied networks, Six-node and TANNET with 30 links respectively. The results in Table 25 show that the proposed approach obtains the optimal solution better than that obtained by [11]. While in Table 26 the reliability values are less than that obtained by [11]. But, lead-time and cost values are less than those obtained by [11]. These results lead to that the proposed algorithm finds the optimal solution.

Table 25. Comparison results for the Six-node network example.

d,t	Aissou's approach			Proposed approach			
	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)
6,7	0.973036	15	510	0.987	0.988833	12	440
6,8	0.987345	14	520	0.999	0.989945	12	460
6,9	0.985979	19	540	0.997	0.989773	14	420
8,9	-			0.999	0.989896	14	420

Table 26. Comparison results for the TANET with 30 linksexample.

d,t	Aissou's approach			Proposed approach			
	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)	best μs	$R_{d,t}$	$S_l(p)$	C(p)
4,16	0.9999745	66	1735	0.993	0.998347	43	1460
6,16	0.999986	61	1435	0.999	0.998934	42	1485
8,18	0.999172		1825	0.998	0.998810	43	1425
9,18	0.985317		1825	0.990	0.997983	44	1515

8. CONCLUSIONS

An approach based on GA with fuzzy optimization is presented in this paper. The presented approach was succeeded to solve the optimal CAP problem in which each components has three attributes; probability, cost, and lead-time. Using fuzzy membership function as fitness, the proposed approach succeeded to find the best optimal solution with maximum system reliability, minimum total assignment cost, and minimum total lead-time in comparison with previous algorithms.

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